

Insect resistance

Tainung 68, the first BPH-resistant Japonica cultivar developed in Taiwan

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Japonica cultivars, which occupy more than 90% of the planted area in Taiwan, are susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH). Efforts to transfer BPH resistance from indica to japonica rices have resulted in the release of BPH-resistant selection Chianung 250, the first BPH-resistant japonica cultivar developed in Taiwan. The Subcommittee on Varietal Registration of the Taiwan Rice Improvement Council unanimously recommended its release 1 June 1982.

The new cultivar, officially named Tainung 68, was selected in 1976 from the cross Nankai-yu 114//Nankai-yu 77//Tainan 5²/ASD 7, made in 1973 at Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station. The resistance to BPH inherited from

Correlations between silvershoots and panicle and tiller numbers

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Gall midge infestation is thought to stimulate profuse tillering. Therefore the association among silvershoots and tiller and panicle numbers was assessed. Data on the three attributes were taken on variety Sita on 27 randomly selected hills from each of 11 plots, 10 treated with insecticides and 1 untreated. Data were collected after the emergence of panicles, about 1 month after insecticides were applied.

Total correlation coefficients between silvershoots and tillers, silvershoots and panicles, and tillers and panicles and partial correlation between silvershoots and panicles were determined. Estimates of total and partial correlation coefficients for the 11 treatments were pooled

Table 1. Resistance^a to disease and insect pest of Tainung 68 in Taiwan, China.

Cultivar	Blast	Neck blast	Bacterial blight	Brown planthopper ^b	
				15 DS	45 DS
Tainung 68	MR-S	MR-S	MR-S	S	R
Tainung 67 (check)	S-HS	S-HS	MS	S	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bDS = days after seeding.

Table 2. Agronomic performance of Tainung 68 in Taiwan, China (av of 1979-81).

Cultivar	Maturity (days)		Height (cm)		Yield ^a (t/ha)	
	1st crop	2d crop	1st crop	2d crop	1st crop	2d crop
Tainung 68	115	97	94	99	6.3	4.6
Tainung 67 (check)	116	98	96	103	6.8	4.6

^aRecorded at Pintung, southern Taiwan.

ASD7 is expressed at late growing stages. Tainung 68 also has some resistance to blast and bacterial leaf blight diseases (Table 1). Most agronomic characters are desirable, with good yields in the second crop, particularly in the southern part of the island (Table 2).

Currently grown cultivar Tainung 67 is susceptible to BPH, which occurs severely in southern Taiwan during the hot, wet second crop season. Tainung 68, is a promising alternative and an important source of BPH resistance in breeding programs. ■

using a multiple covariance model.

Tillering correlated positively with silvershoots (see table). Estimates of correlation coefficients varied from 0.1326 to 0.8402, significant in 9 cases. The pooled correlation coefficient was 0.4718, significant at the 0.01 level.

Tillers correlated positively with pani-

cles. Estimates of coefficients varied from 0.1731 to 0.6898, significant in 9 cases. Estimate of the pooled correlation coefficient (0.5518) was significant at the 0.01 level.

Of 11 estimates of the correlation coefficient between silvershoots and panicles, only one was significant. This sug-

Estimates of total and partial correlation coefficients^a between silvershoots, tillers, and panicle numbers at Bihar, India.

Treatment	r ₁₂	r ₂₃	r ₁₃	r _{13·2}
Foratox	0.8402**	0.6056**	0.0880 ^{ns}	0.9751**
BPMC	0.1326 ^{ns}	0.5227**	0.0096 ^{ns}	0.0936 ^{ns}
Ekalux	0.4002*	0.6898**	0.1438 ^{ns}	0.3536*
Carbofuran	0.5604**	0.3551 ^{ns}	0.2573 ^{ns}	0.5608**
Carbaryl	0.7960**	0.1731 ^{ns}	0.0828 ^{ns}	0.6428**
Lindane	0.4099*	0.5548**	0.2604 ^{ns}	0.6428**
Diazinon	0.6723**	0.5035**	0.4743*	0.2125 ^{ns}
Tamaron	0.3408 ^{ns}	0.6370**	0.2242 ^{ns}	0.6089**
CFVP	0.5467**	0.5563**	0.2653 ^{ns}	0.2444 ^{ns}
Monocil	0.5467**	0.5563**	0.2095 ^{ns}	0.7381**
Control	0.5581**	0.4650*	0.0937 ^{ns}	0.2257 ^{ns}
Pooled	0.4718**	0.5518**	0.0029	0.3156*

^a1 = silvershoots, 2 = tillers, 3 = panicles. * = significant at 5% level. ** = significant at 1% level. ns = not significant.